

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 29(3) (2020) 212-224

EISSN 2543-5426

Physical and Psychological Complications of Mastectomy: The Role of Physiotherapy

Miracle A. Adesina^{1-6,*}, Tolulope I. Olajire^{1,5,7}

¹Slum and Rural Health Initiative Research with Purpose Academy, Lalupon, Nigeria

²Cephas Health Research Initiative Inc, Ibadan, Nigeria

³Mental and Oral Health Development Organization, Kebbi State, Nigeria

⁴Universal Care for Africa Foundation, St Louis, USA

⁵Department of Physiotherapy, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

⁶Department of Physiotherapy, Ring Road State Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria

⁷Department of Physiotherapy, University College Hospital, Ibadan, Nigeria

*E-mail address: miracleadesina5@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Breast cancer affects a large number of women worldwide. Surgical management has evolved towards mastectomies and breast-conserving surgeries. The complications following a mastectomy can be physical and/or psychological. The physical complications include pain, scarring, lymphedema, limitation in range of motion at the shoulder, muscle weakness, change in body posture, etc. Some of the psychological complications are negative body image, anxiety, depression and depressive disorders, negative body image. Appropriate management requires a multi-disciplinary team of which the physiotherapist is a part of. Literature has shown that there is a better improvement in physical function if physiotherapy is commenced early. Therefore, physiotherapy should be incorporated pre- and post-mastectomy. Physiotherapy management should focus on lymphatic drainage, soft tissue mobilization, range of motion exercises, strengthening exercises and postural correction. Increased physical activity and recommendation of support groups can help to improve psychological outcomes. It is the role of the physical therapist to deal with the physical and psychological complications of a mastectomy to improve the quality of life of the patients.

Keywords: Mastectomy, physical complications, breast cancer, psychological complications, physiotherapy

1. INTRODUCTION

Cancer is one of the main causes of mortality worldwide (Momenimovahed and Salehiniya, 2017). Breast cancer originates from breast tissue, mostly from the inner lining of milk ducts or the lobules that supply the ducts with milk. Cancers originating from ducts are known as ductal carcinomas, while those originating from lobules are known as lobular carcinomas (Sariago, 2010). Breast cancer is one of the leading types of cancer in women (Ferlay *et al.*, 2008; Mathew and Perez, 2011).

There are an estimated 2.09 million cases of breast cancer with the death of 627,000 individuals in 2018 (WHO, 2018) and it is estimated to reach 3.2 million by the year 2050 (Hortobagyi *et al.*, 2005). Breast cancer constitutes the most frequent cancer in women between 35 and 54 years old, and the ratio of men to women with it is 1 to 150, and its incidence continually rises (American Cancer Society, 2005). The incidence rate of breast cancer is higher in developed countries and it varies with race and ethnicity (DeSantis *et al.*, 2014). The incidence rate of breast cancer ranges from 19.4 per 100,000 people in East Africa to 89.7 per 100,000 in West Europe, .27 cases per 100, 000 in East Africa and 92 cases per 100,000 in North America (Bray *et al.*, 2018).

The primary treatment for breast cancer is based on the clinical extent and pathological state of the tumour, age of the patient, biological prognostic factors, other diseases of the patient, as well as the desire and psychological state of the patient (Greene *et al.*, 2002; Karki, 2005). Treatment for breast cancer may include breast-conserving surgery, modified radical mastectomy, radiation therapy, induction chemotherapy, prophylactic drugs, etc (Maughan *et al.*, 2010). Through the years, the management of breast cancer has evolved towards mastectomies and breast-conserving surgeries (Franceschini *et al.*, 2015; Al-Gaithy *et al.*, 2019). In the lower stage of advancement of the carcinoma, breast-conserving therapy is used, while in higher stages of advancement of locoregional cancer, a mastectomy is applied (Kamusińska, 2014).

A mastectomy is a surgical procedure that involves the removal of all or part of the breast tissue (Goethals and Rose, 2018). Mastectomy is the surgical treatment of breast cancer which can result in a permanent change in appearance in women (Cebeci *et al.*, 2011). It is considered as a frequently employed surgical choice for patients with the initial or recurring disease. The breast is considered in many cultures to be a representation of femininity, beauty, sexuality, motherhood (Cebeci *et al.*, 2011) thus a mastectomy is considered by many professionals to have physical and psychological complications (Rostkowska *et al.*, 2006). The physical and psychological consequences of mastectomy are well documented ranging from pain and major scarring to psychological distress and sexual dysfunction (Yurek, 2000; Arora *et al.*, 2001; Wilmot, 2001). Women with mastectomy tend to experience mental stress attributable to physical weakness and the potentially lethal prognosis (Harcourt *et al.*, 2003).

Several types of mastectomy procedures are available ranging from Halsted's radical Mastectomy, modified radical (Patey) mastectomy, total or simple mastectomy, skin-sparing mastectomy or nipple- sparing mastectomy among others (Lazaraviciute and Chaturvedi, 2017). A radical (Halsted) mastectomy is a type of mastectomy, where breast tissue, pectoralis major and minor muscles, and all axillary tissues are removed while a modified radical (Patey) mastectomy is a type of mastectomy, where breast tissue and pectoralis minor muscle are removed, together with axillary nodes; It is performed on more invasive tumours (Sweetland , 2006).

A total or simple mastectomy is a type of mastectomy, where breast tissue and involved skin are removed with or without axillary surgery and a skin-sparing mastectomy is on the rise and it is a type of mastectomy where the breast tissue is removed, but skin envelope is preserved (Sweetland, 2006). Complications of mastectomy can be physical, psychological or others.

Upper limb lymphedema, decreased shoulder mobility, neural tissue injuries causing sensory and motor impairments, the pain of the upper body and limb are common post-treatment physical impairments (Gosselink *et al.*, 2003; Rietman *et al.*, 2004). One of the major physical complications of mastectomy is lymphedema of the ipsilateral (affected) arm. Lymphedema is defined as the swelling of the arm which is caused by insufficient lymphatic drainage into lymph nodes. It can result in “cosmetic deformity, loss of functional ability, physical discomfort, recurrent episodes of erysipelas and psychological distress” (Andersen, 2000). It is caused by a defect in the lymphatic system and characterised by an abnormal increase in tissue proteins, oedema, chronic inflammation and fibrosis (Purushotam *et al.*, 2007; Martin *et al.*, 2011). It affects about 30% of those who undergo breast cancer treatment and results in excess fluid accumulation in the interstitial space, detrimental tissue changes, limb swelling and quality of life issues (Williams *et al.*, 2005).

Lymphedema can be divided into 3 stages. During the first ‘reversible’ stage protein-rich oedema is present; in Stage 2, the ‘spontaneously irreversible’ stage, there are fibro sclerotic alterations and an increase in the number of keratinocytes and connective tissue cells. Stage 3, ‘elephantiasis’, is characterized by massive hyperkeratosis and by a tremendous increase in the volume of the limb (Foldi, 1998). It may occur almost subsequently to surgical treatment, during radiotherapy or many months or years after treatment (Kisner and Colby, 2005). Lymphedema can be acute or chronic, depending on whether the onset of symptoms is within 18 months of the surgery. Chronic lymphedema is often difficult to treat (Golshan and Smith, 2006). Symptoms may include swelling, fibrosis, restricted joint mobility and pain (Sleigh and Manna, 2019). Lymphedema following a mastectomy presents a detrimental effect on both physical and psychological health as it lasts for a long time (Armer *et al.*, 2009; Bernas *et al.*, 2010).

Another complication of lymphedema is limited shoulder function following surgery (Budd, 1978). About 7 out of 8 people who undergo any form of surgery for breast cancer experience shoulder and arm problems (Hidding *et al.*, 2014). Around 17 to 32% of people who have undergone a mastectomy have impaired shoulder movement (Box, 2002). A study by Nesvold *et al.*, 2008 shows that women who undergo mastectomy were more likely to experience a restricted range of motion (ROM) compared to women submitted to breast-conserving therapy. The limitation in arm function may be due to the presence of the lymphedema in the affected arm and stiffness after the surgery. Post-mastectomy pain of the thoracic wall limits the mobility of the shoulder directly after surgery and may persist for longer periods. Also, there could be muscle atrophy of the shoulder muscles due to intraoperative damage to the nerves can lead to a limitation in shoulder function (Ashikari, 1984).

Radical surgical treatment of patients with breast cancer may contribute to a change in body posture. A significant complication of mastectomy is changing in body posture due to the limitation of movements and soreness of the spine (Rostkowska E *et al.*, 2006). Damaged muscle weakness, pain associated with extensive postoperative wound, a reflexive attempt to compensate for the absence of the breast as well as soft tissue fibrosis as a result of radiotherapy are the direct causes of negative changes in the posture of women after mastectomy (Al Ghazar *et al.*, 2000; Janni *et al.*, 2001).

Lymphatic oedema also contributes to the intensification of disorders in body posture (Vaças and Ryan, 2003). Båk and Cieśla (2009) showed the presence of posture defects in 82.3% of women after breast amputation compared with only 35.1% in apparently healthy women. Women after mastectomy have an increased tendency to exhibit kyphotic posture and to tilt the trunk forward (Båk and Cieśla, 2012). The significant alterations include a greater trunk inclination angle, greater symmetry of scapula position, a greater angle of pelvis twisting, greater forward-leaning of the trunk, greater total value of angles of spinal curvatures, etc. (Rostkowska E *et al.*, 2006).

Axillary Web Syndrome/ lymphatic cording is another physical complication that can arise in patients following treatment for breast cancer. Axillary Web Syndrome is a ropelike structure that develops mainly under the axilla but can extend to involve the medial aspect of the ipsilateral arm down to the antecubital fossa (Tilley *et al.*, 2009). It is described as the appearance of a palpable cord that begins at the axilla and spreads down the arm even at times as far as the thumb (Moskovitz *et al.*, 2001). It tends to develop after axillary surgery for breast cancer. Lymphatic cording can also be associated with pain and limitation of shoulder movement (Tilley *et al.*, 2009). The incidence of this syndrome has been described to be between 6-72% among various authors (Tengrup *et al.*, 2000; Moskovitz *et al.*, 2001; Leidenius *et al.*, 2003).

Other complications may include pain, scar tissue, musculoskeletal issues, brachial plexus injury, deconditioning and endurance deficits, fatigue, balance and falls (Silver and Gilchrist, 2011). Pain and scar tissue is due to the mastectomy. It can further lead to pain syndromes (Rietman *et al.*, 2003). The surgical procedure may lead to transient or permanent damage to the nerves in the surgical area thus a brachial plexus injury (Kim *et al.*, 2016). Radiotherapy following breast surgery may also have a considerable effect on brachial plexus injury (Eyüp and Ethem, 2018). Impairments may be manifested by the loss of all types of sensation (pain, touch, temperature), flaccid paralysis of muscles, and atrophy of muscle groups on the surgical side, paraesthesia, tingling sensation, and perspiration (Mika, 2005).

Some psychological problems can occur after a mastectomy. The removal of a woman's breast can lead to perceived losses by the woman consequently leading to psychosocial problems (Gumus, 2006). Literature has shown that patients with breast cancer, who lose part of all of their breast tissue, can experience changes in body image, self-concept, emotions, behaviour, family dynamics, and the roles of patient and family (Ozbas, 2006). Negative body image among breast cancer survivors among those who have undergone a mastectomy includes dissatisfaction with appearance, perceived loss of femininity and body integrity, reluctance to look at one self's naked, feeling less sexually attractive and self-conscious about appearances (Fobair *et al.*, 2006). Another psychosocial complication of mastectomy is depression and depressive disorders (Meyerowitz, 1980).

Another troublesome phenomenon is experiencing anxiety and fear overtime of the diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer. (Yi and Syrjala, 2017). Anxiety is the most expected response for patients affected by a malignant disease and facing a surgical procedure (Montebarocci *et al.*, 2007).

Fears and concerns regarding death and reoccurrence of breast cancer and also a form of change in femininity, sexuality, and attractiveness are important issues that need to be dealt with (Baucom, 2006). Anllo (2000) and Bakwell (2006) revealed that shock of being recognized for cancer and its treatment can exert a major effect on physical and mental states of the patients' sexual relationships.

It is also likely the patient to become deeply dependent on others, as a result of undergoing mastectomy. The psychological complications of lymphedema can decrease patients' abilities and efficacy at work and home (Abbasi *et al.*, 2018). Change in occupational status is another aftermath that may happen, such a change has the potential to affect the relationship between the patient and her family or society (Kraus, 1999). Crouch and McKenzie (2000) revealed that patients that have undergone mastectomy suffer from a feeling of not having body balance which is the main factor in physical attractiveness, and lack of mental peace as an indicator in mental attractiveness because of fear from disease recurrence and death hazard. Both factors result in a reduction of quality of life to a great extent (Crouch and Mckenzie, 2000). It is important that a woman in such difficult moments is provided with support and help of the closest relatives as well as professional, comprehensive care of medical personnel (Lewicka *et al.*, 2015) to improve their quality of life (Fouladi, 2013). However, the rehabilitation of the psyche is less commonly reported leading to poor coping strategies (Loh and Musa, 2015).

Patients often require complete medical and psychological support with a multi-disciplinary team that includes doctors, nurses, psychiatrists, physical therapists, psychologists, dieticians, and pharmacists (Chirgwin *et al.*, 2010). This team would be used to aid the healing process of the patient and further push the acceptance of their body (Montebarocci *et al.*, 2007).

Physiotherapy is a very important part of the team and should be incorporated pre and immediately post-operation. A comprehensive physiotherapy program should be individualised according to the presenting complaints of the patient. Pre-operatively, education should be carried out for exercises applied after surgery, as well as education of patients concerning the code of conduct in daily life (Kamusińska *et al.*, 2014).

Physical therapy is a way to manage lymphedema. According to the International Society of Lymphology, the treatment protocol of reduction of breast cancer lymphedema includes manual lymphatic drainage (MLD), compression bandaging, active exercises, and skincare. Manual lymphatic drainage uses massage techniques to encourage the removal of excess interstitial fluid, increase lymphatic transport into lymph nodes and soften fibrotic tissues (Foldi *et al.*, 2003). Limb exercises can be progressive, resistive, free or isometric and can help to improve the lymphatic drainage of the affected limb (Johansson *et al.*, 2004). The patient is also recommended and fitted with a compression garment (Bernas *et al.*, 2010). A phase of management called the Complex Decongestive Physical Therapy (CDPT) is used to effect this protocol. It covers the following two subsequent phases of therapy; the first one is an intensive phase, aimed at a maximum reduction of oedema by daily use of manual lymphatic drainage therapy, multi-layer compression bandaging, and exercises improving lymph outflow (Ograczyk *et al.*, 2004; Dos *et al.*, 2004). The second phase is a maintenance-optimization phase, which is aimed at fixation and maintenance of the effects of therapy obtained during the first phase. It includes self-massage, compression therapy in the form of elastic compression materials, and exercises improving lymph outflow. This phase usually covers the entire life of the patient due to the chronic character of the problem (Pyszora, 2010).

The literature revealed that there is significantly better shoulder function following early physiotherapy in patients who have had a mastectomy. Physical therapy treatment for upper extremity complications can include soft tissue mobilizations, range of motion exercises, strengthening exercises, postural assessment among others (DeGroef *et al.*, 2015; Cho *et al.*, 2016). Mobilization of scars can also be done using massage techniques (Zanier and Bordon, 2015). It is also necessary for the patient to undergo rehabilitation to minimise the changes in body posture (Kopański *et al.*, 2003, Rostkowska *et al.*, 2006).

Properly selected exercises such as learning the correct way of breathing as well as monitoring the changes of posture during the rehabilitation process will not only enable a woman to avoid wrong compensation but also to considerably improve the posture (McAnaw and Harris, 2002).

Physical therapy is also useful for better psychological complications of mastectomy. Rehabilitation in the form of physical therapy following a mastectomy can help to improve the self-image of women who underwent a mastectomy and have a positive effect on their minds (Moyer and Salovey, 1999). Physical activity generally is of benefit for cancer patients including reduced fatigue, nausea, body fat, anxiety and depression and increased muscle strength, lean body mass, aerobic capacity, enhanced immune function, and improved quality of life (Galva and Newton, 2005).

Aerobic exercises have shown to be beneficial for cancer patients who are undergoing treatment. Mock *et al.* reported that home-based walking at a moderate intensity (50-70% of maximum heart rate), performed for 10 to 45 minutes per day, 4 to 6 days per week, for one to six months, during chemotherapy and radiation treatment for breast cancer reduced cancer-related fatigue, sleep disruption, depression, and anxiety while improving cardiopulmonary function and Quality of Life. The aerobic training also increases the patient's self-confidence and independence (Pattanshetty and Chopde, 2016). Low resistance training can also be performed with the aid dumbbells, resistance bands, or even bodyweight (Pattanshetty and Chopde, 2016). Resistance training performed 3 days per week for 12 weeks has been shown to improve cancer-related fatigue, cognitive function, Quality Of Life, and muscular strength (Pattanshetty and Chopde, 2016).

In patients with complete mobility and without oedema, self-massage, respiratory exercises, general fitness exercises, and active recreation are recommended (Kamusińska, 2014). Health education about behaviour in daily living, prevention of secondary lymphoedema can also be done by a physiotherapist (Kamusińska, 2014).

Health professionals such as a physiotherapist may refer a client to see a psychologist or psychiatrist. A physical therapist may also recommend support groups that can provide information on how to cope with the breast cancer situation (Zhi *et al.*, 2017). Literature shows that exercise in the form of physical activity can help to improve mood, anxiety, and depression (Pinto and Maruyama, 1999). Properly selected exercises can help to improve posture. This can then help to improve the better image of oneself and the improvement of the quality of life (McAnaw and Harris, 2002). Relaxation techniques can be used to reduce psychological distress and improve the mood in breast cancer patients (Tatrow and Montgomery, 2006). Also, the satisfaction gained from the results achieved during exercises and physical fitness necessary for the performance of various social roles translates into restored self-esteem and fulfilment in professional as well as family life (Zyznawska *et al.*, 2015).

2. CONCLUSIONS

A mastectomy is a surgical procedure that can cause many changes in a woman's life. It has many physical dysfunctions and psychological consequences as time goes by. Rehabilitation is a major part of the process of treatment of breast cancer, and its primary goal is the limitation of selected physical, psychological, and social consequences of the disease. An interdisciplinary team should be focused on achieving rehabilitation goals.

Rehabilitation for women who have undergone a mastectomy should be broader and more proactive to include physical and psychological. It is the role of the physiotherapist to not only aid with the physical symptoms but also the psychological to improve the quality of life of the woman.

References

- [1] Abbasi, B, Mirzakhany, N, Angooti Oshnari, L, Irani, A, Hosseinzadeh, S, Tabatabaei, SM, *et al.* (2018). The effect of relaxation techniques on edema, anxiety and depression in post- mastectomy lymphedema patients undergoing comprehensive decongestive therapy: A clinical trial. *PLoS ONE* 13(1): e0190231.
- [2] Al-Gaithy, ZK, Yaghmoor, BE, Koumu, MI, Alshehri, KA, Saqah AA, and Alshehri HZ. (2019). Trends of mastectomy and breast-conserving surgery and related factors in female breast cancer patients treated at King Abdulaziz University Hospital, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, 2009–2017: A retrospective cohort study. *Annals of Medicine and Surgery* 41: 47–52.
- [3] Al-Ghazal, SK, Fallowfield, L, and Blamey, RW (2000). Comparison of psychological aspects and patient satisfaction following breast conserving surgery, simple mastectomy and breast reconstruction. *European Journal of Cancer* 36: 938–43.
- [4] American Cancer Society. (2005) Cancer Facts and Figures. Available at: <https://www.cancer.org/content/dam/cancer-org/research/cancer-facts-and-statistics/annual-cancer-facts-and-figures/2005/cancer-facts-and-figures-2005.pdf> Accessed 22nd January 2020.
- [5] Andersen, L, Højris, I, Erlandsen, M, and Andersen, J (2000). Treatment of breast-cancer-related lymphedema with or without manual lymphatic drainage--a randomized study. *Acta Oncology* 39(3): 399–405.
- [6] Anllo, LM, (2000). Sexual life after breast cancer. *Journal of Sex and Marital Therapy* 3: 241-8.
- [7] Armer, JM, Stewart, BR, and Shook, RP (2009). 30-month post-breast cancer treatment lymphoedema. *Journal of Lymphoedema* 4(1): 14–18.
- [8] Arora, NK, Gustafson, DH, Hawkins, RP, McTavish, F, cella DF, Pingree S, Mendenhall JH, and Mahvi DM (2001). Impact of surgery and chemotherapy on the quality of life of younger women with breast carcinoma: a prospective study. *Cancer* 92(5): 1288-98.
- [9] Ashikari, R, Farrow, JH, and O'Hara, J (1984). Fibroadenomas in the breast of juveniles. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment* 4: 117–128.
- [10] Bąk, M and Cieśla, S (2009). Assessment of postural disorders in women after radical mastectomy followed by immediate breast Reconstruction. *Physiotherapy* 17(1):30-37.
- [11] Bakewell, RT and Volker, DL (2006). Sexual dysfunction related to the treatment of young women with breast cancer. *Clinical Journal of Oncology and Nursing* 6: 697-702.

- [12] Baucom, D.H, Porter, L.S., Kirby, J.S., Gremore, T.M., and Keefe, F.J. (2006). Psychosocial issues confronting young women with cancer. *Breast Disease* 23: 103–113.
- [13] Bernas, M, Askew, R, Armer J, and Cormier JN (2010). Lymphedema: how do we diagnose and reduce the risk of this dreaded complication of breast cancer treatment? *Current Breast Cancer Reports* 2(1): 53–58
- [14] Box, RC, Reul-Hirche, HM, Bullock-Saxton, JE, and Furnival, CM (2002). Shoulder movement after breast cancer surgery: results of a randomised controlled study of postoperative physiotherapy. *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment* 75(1): 35-50.
- [15] Bray, F, Ferlay, J, Soerjomataram, I, Siegel, RL, Torre, LA, and Jemal, A (2018) Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA- A Cancer Journal for Clinicians* 68(6):394-424.
- [16] Budd, DC, Cochran, RC, Sturtz, DL, and Fouty, WJ Jr (1978). Surgical morbidity after mastectomy operations. *American Journal of Surgery* 135: 218–220.
- [17] Cebeci, F, Yangın, HB, and Tekel, A (2012). Life experiences of women with breast cancer in south western Turkey: a qualitative study. *European Journal of Oncology and Nursing* 16(4): 406-12.
- [18] Chirgwin, J, Craike, M, Gray, C, Watty, K, Mileskin, L, and Patricia, M (2010). Does Multidisciplinary Care Enhance the Management of Advanced Breast Cancer?: Evaluation of Advanced Breast Cancer Multidisciplinary Team Meetings'. *Livingston Journal of Oncology Practice* 6(6): 294–300.
- [19] Cho, Y, Chang, JS, Rha, KH, Hong, SJ, Choi YD, Ham WS, Kim JW, and Cho J (2016). Does Radiotherapy for the Primary Tumor Benefit Prostate Cancer Patients with Distant Metastasis at Initial Diagnosis. *PLoS ONE* 11(1): e0147191.
- [20] Cieśla, S and Bąk M (2012). The Effect of Breast Reconstruction on Maintaining a Proper Body Posture in Patients after Mastectomy, *Breast Reconstruction - Current Techniques*. IntechOpen, DOI: 10.5772/29373.
- [21] Crouch, M and McKenzie, H (2000). Social realities of loss and suffering following mastectomy. *Health* 2: 196-215.
- [22] De Groef , A, Marijke Van Kampen, Evi D, Marie-Rose C, Patrick N, Inge G, and Nele D (2015). Effectiveness of postoperative physical therapy for upper-limb impairments after breast cancer treatment: a systematic review. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation* 96(6): 1140–1153.
- [23] DeSantis, CE, Lin, CC, Mariotto, AB, Siegel, RL, Stein, KD, Kramer JL, Alteri R, Robbins AS, and Jemal A (2014). Cancer treatment and survivorship statistics. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians* 64(4): 252-71.
- [24] Doś, J, Górska-Doś, M, and Szuba, A (2005). The integrated and interdisciplinary treatment of chronic lymphoedema. *Annales Academiae Medicae Bialostocensis* 50:141-4.

- [25] Eyüp, MY and Ethem, B (2018). Brachial Plexus Injury in Abdominal and Breast Surgery. *Surgery and Medicine Open Access Journal* 2(1) DOI: 10.31031/SMOAJ.2018.02.000526
- [26] Ferlay, J, Shin, HR, Bray, F, Forman, D, Mathers, C, and Parkin, DM (2008). Estimates of worldwide burden of cancer in 2008: GLOBOCAN 2008. *International Journal of Cancer* 127(12): 2893-917.
- [27] Földi, E (1998). Treatment of lymphedema and patient rehabilitation. *Anticancer Research* 18: 2211–2212.
- [28] Foldi, M, Foldi, E, and Kubik, S, Eds (2003). Textbook of lymphology for physicians and lymphedema therapists' Urban & Fisher, San Francisco
- [29] Forbair, P, Stewart, S, Chang, S, *et al.* (2006). Body image and sexual problems in young women with breast cancer. *Psychology and Oncology* 15: 579-94.
- [30] Fouladi, N, Pourfarzi, F, Mazaheri, E, Alimohammadi Asl, H, Rezaie, M, Amani, F, and Nejad, MR (2013). Beliefs and behaviors of breast cancer screening in women referring to health care centers in northwest Iran according to the champion health belief model scale. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention* 14(11): 6857–6862.
- [31] Franceschini, G, Martin, SA, Di Leone, A, Magno, S, Moschella, F, *et al.* (2015). New trends in breast cancer surgery: a therapeutic approach increasingly efficacy and respectful of the patient. *II Giornale di Chirurgia*, 36(4): 145-52.
- [32] Galvão, DA and Newton, RU (2005). Review of exercise intervention studies in cancer patients. *Journal of Clinical Oncology* 23(4): 899–909.
- [33] Goethals, A and Rose, J (2019), 'Mastectomy' In: Stat Pearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing.
- [34] Golshan, M and Smith, B (2006). Prevention and management of arm lymphedema in the patient with breast cancer. *Journal of Supportive Oncology* 4(8): 381-6.
- [35] Gosselink, R, Rouffaer, L, Vanhelden, P, Piot, W, Troosters, T, and Christiaens, MR (2003). Recovery of upper limb function after axillary dissection. *Journal of Surgery and Oncology*, 83(4): 204-11.
- [36] Greene, FL, Stewart, AK, and Norton, HJ (2002). A New TNM Staging Strategy for Node-Positive (Stage III) Colon Cancer. An Analysis of 50,042 Patients. *Annals of Surgery* 236(4): 416–421.
- [37] Gumus, M., Yumuk, P.F., Salepci, T., M. Aliustaoglu, F. Dane, M. Ekenel, G. Basaran, H. Kaya, N. Barisik, and N.S. Turhal (2006). HPV DNA frequency and subset analysis in human breast cancer patients' normal and tumoral tissue samples. *Journal of Experimental and Clinical Cancer Research* 25(4): 515–521.
- [38] Harcourt, D.M., Rumsey, N.J., Ambler, N.R. Cawthorn, S.J., Reid C.D., Maddox P.R., Kenealy J.M., Rainsburg R.M., and Umpleby H.C. (2003). The psychological effect of mastectomy with or without breast reconstruction: a prospective, multicenter study. *Plastic Reconstructive Surgery* 111(3) 1060–1068.

- [39] Hidding, JT, Carien H. G. Beurskens, Philip J. van der Wees, Hanneke WM van Laarhoven, and Maria WG Nijhuis-van der Sanden (2014). Treatment Related Impairments in Arm and Shoulder in Patients with Breast Cancer: A Systematic Review. *PLoS One* 9(5): e96748.
- [40] Hortobagyi, GN, de la Garza Salazar, J, Pritchard, K, Amadori ,D, Haldiner R, Hudis CA, Khaled H, Liu M, Martin M, Namer M, O'Shaughnessy JA, Shen ZZ, and Albain KS, ABREAST Investigators (2005). The global breast cancer burden: variations in epidemiology and survival. *Clinical Breast Cancer* 6(5): 391-401.
- [41] Janni,W, Rjosk, D, Dimpfl, TH, Haertl K, Strobl B, Hepp F, Hanke A, Bergauer F, Sommer H (2001). Quality of life influenced by primary surgical treatment for stage I-III breast cancer. Long term follow up of a matched pair analysis. *Annals of Surgery and Oncology* 8: 542-8.
- [42] Johansson, JE, Andrén, O, Andersson, SO, Dickman, PW, Holmberg, L, Magnuson, A, and Adami HO (2004). Natural history of early, localized prostate cancer. *Journal of the American Medical Association* 291(22): 2713-2719.
- [43] Kamusińska, E, Ciosek, M, and Karwat ID (2014). The importance of rehabilitation in the treatment of breast cancer. *Medical Studies* 30(3), 214-220.
- [44] Kärki, A, Simonen, R, Mälkiä, E, and Selfe, J (2018). Impairments, activity limitations and participation restrictions 6 and 12 months after breast cancer operation. *CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians* 68(6): 394-424.
- [45] Kim, YD, Yu, JY, Shim, J, Heo, HJ, and Kim, H (2016). Risk of encountering dorsal scapular and long thoracic nerves during ultrasound-guided interscalene brachial plexus block with nerve stimulator. *The Korean Journal of Pain* 29(3): 179-184
- [46] Kisner, C and Colby, LA (2005). Exercícios Terapêuticos Fundamentos e Técnicas. São Paulo (SP): Manole
- [47] Kopanski Z, Wojewoda T, Wojewoda A, Schlegel-Zawadzka M, Wozniacka R, Suder A, and Kosciuk T (2003) Influence of some anthropometric parameters on the risk of development of distal complications after mastectomy carried out because of breast carcinoma. *American Journal of Human Biology* 15(3): 433-9.
- [48] Kraus, PL (1999). Body image, decision making, and breast cancer treatment. *Cancer and Nursing* 22: 421-7.
- [49] Lazaraviciute, G and Chaturvedi, S (2017). Mastectomy - A Critical Review. *Open Journal of Clinical Diagnostics* 7: 58-66.
- [50] Leidenius, M, E Leppanen, L, Krogerus, L, and von Smitten K (2003). Motion restriction and axillary web syndrome after sentinel node biopsy and axillary clearance in breast cancer. *American Journal of Surgery* 185: 127-130.
- [51] Lewicka, M, Sulima, M, Bakalczuk, G, and Pyć, M (2015). Prevention and early detection of breast cancer. *Journal of Public Health Nursing and Medical Rescue* 2: 11-16.

- [52] Loh, S and Musa, A (2015). Methods to Improve Rehabilitation of Patients Following Breast Cancer Surgery: A Review of Systematic Reviews. *Breast Cancer: Targets and Therapy* 7:81-98.
- [53] Martín, ML, Hernández, MA, Avendaño, C, Rodriguez F, and Martinez H (2011). Manual lymphatic drainage therapy in patients with breast cancer related lymphoedema. *BMC Cancer* 11: 94
- [54] Mathew, J and Perez, EA (2011). Trastuzumab emtansine in human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive breast cancer: a review. *Current Opinion in Oncology* 23(6): 594-600.
- [55] Maughan, KL, Lutterbie, MA, and Ham, PS (2010). Treatment of breast cancer. *American Family Physician* 81(11): 1339-46.
- [56] McAnaw, MB and Harris, KW (2002). The role of physical therapy in the rehabilitation of patients with mastectomy and breast reconstruction. *Breast Disease* 16: 163–174.
- [57] Meyerowitz, BE (1980). Psychosocial correlates of breast cancer and its treatments. *Psychology Bulletin* 87(1), 108-31.
- [58] Mika, KA (2005). Po odjęciu piersi [Polish]. Wydawnictwo Lekarskie PZWL, Warszawa 13: 133.
- [59] Momenimovahed, Z and Salehiniya, H (2017). Incidence, mortality and risk factors of cervical cancer in the world. *Biomedical Research and Therapy* 4(12): 1795-1811.
- [60] Montebanocci, O., Lo Dato, F., Baldaro, B., Morselli, P., and Rossi, N.C. (2007). Anxiety and body satisfaction before and six months after mastectomy and breast reconstruction surgery. *Psychological Reports* 101: 100–106
- [61] Moskovitz, AH, Anderson BO, Yeung, RS, Byrd DR, Lawton TJ, and Moe RE (2001) Axillary web syndrome after axillary dissection. *American Journal of Surgery* 181: 434-439.
- [62] Moyer, A, Salovey, P, and Casey-Cannon, S. (1999) Challenges facing female doctoral students and recent graduates. *Psychology of Women Quarterly* 23(3): 607–630.
- [63] Nesvold, IL, Alv A. Dahl, Løkkevik, E, Mengshoel, AM, and Fossa, SD (2008). Arm and shoulder morbidity in breast cancer patients after breast-conserving therapy versus mastectomy. *Acta Oncologica* 47: 835-842
- [64] Ograczyk, A, Kaszuba, A, Miękoś-Zydek, B, et al. (2004). Współczesne metody leczenia obrzęków chłonnych [Polish]: The importance of rehabilitation in the treatment of breast cancer. *Dermatologia Estetyczna* 5: 251-5.
- [65] Özbaş, A. (2006). Meme kanserli ailelerde sorunlar ve çözümler (problems and solutions of breast cancer families). *Meme Sağlığı Dergisi* 2: 115-7
- [66] Pattanshetty, RB, and Chopde, C (2016). Role of Physiotherapy in Cancer-Related Fatigue in Cancer Survivors - A Narrative Review. *Journal of Novel Physiotherapy and Physical Rehabilitation* 3(1): 030-034.
- [67] Pinto, BM and Maruyama, NC (1999). Exercise in the rehabilitation of breast cancer survivors. *Psycho-Oncology* 8(3): 191–206.

- [68] Purushotham, AD, Bennett Britton, TM, Klevesath, MB, Chou P, Agbaje OF, and Stephen W (2007). Lymph Node Status and Breast Cancer-related Lymphedema. *Duffy Annals of Surgery* 246(1): 42–45.
- [69] Pyszora, A. (2010). Kompleksowa fizjoterapia pacjentów z obrzękiem limfatycznym [Polish]. *Medycyna Paliatywna w Praktyce* 4, 23-29.
- [70] Rietman, JS, Dijkstra, PU, Geertzen, JH, Baas, P, De Vries, J, Dolsma, W, Groothoff, JW, Eisma, WH, and Hoekstra, HJ (2003). Short-term morbidity of the upper limb after sentinel lymph node biopsy or axillary lymph node dissection for Stage I or II breast carcinoma. *Cancer* 98(4): 690-6
- [71] Rostkowska, E, Bak, M, and Samborski, W (2006). Body posture in women after mastectomy and its changes as a result of rehabilitation. *Advances in Medical Science* 51: 287–297.
- [72] Sario, J (2010). Breast cancer in the young patient. *American Surgery* 76(12): 1397-400.
- [73] Silver, JK and Gilchrist, LS (2011). Cancer rehabilitation with a focus on evidence-based outpatient physical and occupational therapy interventions. *American Journal of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation* 90(5): S5–15.
- [74] Sleight BC and Manna B. (2019). Lymphedema. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing
- [75] Sweetland, HM (2006). Surgery for Breast Cancer. *Women's Health Medicine* 3: 31-33
- [76] Tatrow, K and Montgomery, GH (2006). Cognitive behavioral therapy techniques for distress and pain in breast cancer patients: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Behavioral Medicine* 29(1): 17-27.
- [77] Tengrup, I, L Tenvall-Nitbby, I Christiansson, and Laurin M (2000). Arm Morbidity after breast conserving therapy for breast cancer. *Acta Oncologica* 39: 393-397.
- [78] Tilley, A, Thomas-Maclean, R, and Kwan, W (2009). Lymphatic cording or axillary web syndrome after breast cancer surgery. *Canadian Journal of Surgery* 52(4): 105-106.
- [79] Vaqas, B and Ryan, TJ (2003). Lymphoedema: Pathophysiology and management in resource-poor settings - relevance for lymphatic filariasis control programmes. *Filaria Journal* 2: 4.
- [80] Williams, AF (2005). Lymphedema: estimating the size of the problem. *Palliative Medicine* 19(4): 300-313.
- [81] Wilmoth, MC (2001). The aftermath of breast cancer: an altered sexual self. *Cancer and Nursing* 24(4): 278-86.
- [82] World Health Organization. (2018). Breast cancer. Available at: <https://www.who.int/cancer/prevention/diagnosis-screening/breast-cancer/en/>
- [83] Yi, JC and Syrjala KL (2017). Anxiety and Depression in Cancer Survivors. *Medical Clinics of North America* 101(6):1099-1113.

- [84] Yurek, D, Farrar, W, and Andersen, BL (2000). Breast cancer surgery: comparing surgical groups and determining individual differences in postoperative sexuality and body change stress. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology* 68(4): 697-709.
- [85] Zanier, E and Bordoni, B (2015). A multidisciplinary approach to scars: a narrative review. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare* 8: 59–363.
- [86] Zhi XN, Mei SO, Tamilarasi J, Shuo, and Celestial TY (2017). Breast Cancer: Exploring the Facts and Holistic Needs during and beyond Treatment. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 5(2): 26. doi: 10.3390/healthcare5020026
- [87] Zyznawska, J., Smoąg, D., Brzostek, M., and Kulesa-Mrowiecka, M. (2015). Influence of Physical Activity in the Water to Improve the Quality of Life and Motor Skills, of People with Intellectual Disabilities', [Article in Polish]. *Zdrowie Publiczne i Zarządzanie* 13(3): 275–282.